

TBF-CM: A Transformer-Based Beamforming Framework Leveraging Correlation Matrix Information

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Abstract—This paper introduces TBF-CM, a transformer-based beamforming framework that leverages correlation matrix data. The core contribution is a transformer-based neural network (TNN) designed to map correlation matrices to beamforming weights for a 16-element uniform linear array (ULA) in scenarios accommodating up to seven incoming signals. The capability of TBF-CM to generate complex feeding weights for precise main lobe steering is benchmarked against two advanced NN architectures: a residual NN (ResNet) and a convolutional NN (CNN). Extensive evaluations consider prediction accuracy, inference time, and radiation pattern precision. Results indicate that TBF-CM achieves the lowest prediction errors, especially as the number of incoming signals grows, underscoring its robust generalization in challenging beamforming contexts. Although ResNet accurately identifies null positions, it exhibits marginally higher error rates, while CNN maintains close alignment with the ground truth but incurs greater deviations in side lobes. Inference time analysis reveals that TBF-CM achieves a balanced trade-off between accuracy and efficiency, making it well-suited for real-time applications. While ResNet offers the fastest inference at the expense of accuracy, CNN, despite its high precision, imposes the greatest computational overhead, limiting its suitability for latency-sensitive systems. Finally, radiation pattern comparisons further attest to the superiority of TBF-CM, showing stable main lobe steering and effective side-lobe suppression. Altogether, these findings position TBF-CM as a highly efficient approach for next-generation wireless communication systems.

Index Terms—Transformers, beamforming weights, correlation matrices, uniform linear arrays, and neural networks.

I. INTRODUCTION

IN contemporary wireless telecommunication and radar systems, beamforming plays a crucial role in enhancing the directivity of signal transmission and reception toward the desired direction. This technique involves determining the optimal weights for the antenna array elements to shape a main lobe that aligns with the direction of the desired signal while simultaneously generating nulls to suppress interference from undesired signals [1], [2]. Traditional beamforming algorithms are well-regarded for their efficiency and accuracy, including methods such as least mean squares (LMS) [3], recursive least squares (RLS) [4], minimum variance distortionless response

(MVDR) [5], and null steering beamforming (NSB) [6]. However, these algorithms necessitate substantial computational resource demands and extended processing times for implementation. Moreover, in dynamic environments characterized by several parameters such as user location, signal strength, and surrounding noise, these algorithms may struggle to maintain the expected level of performance consistently.

Direction of arrival (DoA) estimation is essential in enhancing spectral efficiency and enabling optimal beamforming in modern communication systems. It involves identifying the angles of arrival (AoA) of incoming signals received by antenna elements, typically utilizing signal samples [7] or the spatial correlation matrix [8], [9]. Traditional algorithms such as Capon [10], multiple signal classification (MUSIC) [11], [12], and estimation of signal parameters via rotational invariance techniques (ESPRIT) [13], [14] have shown strong performance but often require careful array calibration and are computationally intensive. Traditional beamforming techniques rely on AoA estimates to compute steering weights [15], [16], while several methods use correlation matrices directly to enhance robustness under noise or signal correlation [17]–[19].

Neural networks (NNs) have gained substantial trust across domains due to their strong performance in past and recent research. Given the limitations of traditional beamforming and DoA estimation algorithms and the potential of NNs to overcome them, NN-based approaches have become a major focus. NNs are valued for their ability to learn, adapt to complex patterns, and handle the non-linear nature of beamforming tasks [20], [21]. Although deep NNs (DNNs), or deep learning (DL), introduce computational complexity, their advantages outweigh these costs, making them a compelling alternative to conventional techniques [22].

This paper introduces TBF-CM, a transformer-based beamforming framework designed to leverage correlation matrix information for predicting optimal beamforming weights, thereby shaping the radiation pattern of a uniform linear array (ULA) with M elements. Given the high-dimensional nature of correlation matrix data, the proposed approach effectively addresses the challenge of computing beamforming weights in complex multi-signal environments. By extracting spatial signal characteristics from the correlation matrix, this method enhances beamforming precision and contributes to further advancements in beamforming technology. The essence of this study is the application of transformer-based NNs (TNNs) in

This research was supported by the European Union, through the Horizon Europe Marie Skłodowska-Curie Staff Exchanges Programme “6G intelligent connectivity and interaction for users and infrastructures (6G-ICARUS)” under Grant 101131342.

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beamforming, utilizing their attention mechanism to accurately predict complex feeding weights for ULA elements. To the best of the authors' knowledge, this work represents the first application of TNNs in beamforming that exploits correlation matrix information for a ULA handling up to seven signals, where the first is the desired signal and the remaining ones are treated as interference. The key contributions of this work are summarized as follows:

- We introduce TBF-CM, a transformer-based beamforming framework that maps correlation matrices to beamforming weights using self-attention, enabling enhanced spatial feature extraction.
- TBF-CM is extensively compared against residual NN (ResNet) and convolutional NN (CNN) across multi-signal scenarios (3 to 7 signals), evaluating prediction accuracy, computational efficiency, and radiation pattern precision.
- Experimental results confirm that TBF-CM achieves the lowest RMSE, MAE, and Huber loss, demonstrating robust generalization in complex beamforming tasks.
- Although ResNet provides the fastest inference, TBF-CM maintains an optimal balance between accuracy and efficiency, making it a practical choice for real-time beamforming applications.
- TBF-CM effectively reconstructs beamforming patterns, achieving results comparable to ResNet in main lobe steering and null positioning, thereby enhancing interference suppression with improved precision.

This study lays the groundwork for optimized TNN with reduced inference latency, driving advancements in DL-based beamforming for next-generation wireless communication systems. The remainder of the paper is organized as follows: Section II reviews related work on NN-based beamforming. Section III defines the problem under investigation with the proposed beamforming approach. Section IV describes the NN architectures explored in this study and the training configuration. Section V provides the simulation results and evaluates the performance using various assessment metrics. Finally, the paper concludes with a summary in Section VI.

II. PRIOR WORK

Over recent years, the application of machine learning (ML), particularly NNs, in beamforming has grown rapidly, offering solutions to challenges where traditional techniques struggled to address [23], [24]. These advances have also influenced broader areas of antenna system design, especially in beamforming and multiple-input multiple-output (MIMO) configurations. For instance, [25] integrates ML into a system-by-design framework to enhance electromagnetic computations, improving reliability and reducing cost. Additionally, ML-based digital twin models have been proposed to reflect array antenna design, enabling precise performance prediction and real-time optimization [26]. DL has also enabled progress in forward and inverse problems in electromagnetics, such as inverse scattering and nondestructive testing, achieving superior accuracy and efficiency [27]. Overall, in several research, NN architectures effectively replicate, outperform, or enhance

traditional beamforming synthesis processes, especially in scenarios including practical constraints, real-time control, or physics-driven design requirements [6], [28]–[30].

Recent advances in beamforming have capitalized on the strengths of ResNet to improve adaptability in complex signal environments [31]–[33]. Meanwhile, CNNs have proven highly effective in beamforming for synthetic aperture radar systems, efficiently mitigating interference [34], and enhancing the efficiency of beamforming in noisy environments [35]. However, ResNet is fundamentally built upon stacked convolutional layers, which may restrict its ability to capture long-range spatial interactions, particularly in scenarios with resource constraints. This also applies to CNNs, which basically depend on localized receptive fields and feature extraction. In such scenarios, attention mechanisms become particularly beneficial, as they eliminate the need for deep stacks of convolutional or recurrent layers by allowing each input element to access global context through only $\mathcal{O}(N^2)$ operations. This innovation enables each position in the input sequence to access information from all other positions, significantly improving processing efficiency [36]–[39].

TNN is one of the remarkable advancements in NN design [40], used to model global contextual relationships, making it a strong candidate for beamforming tasks that require long-range spatial awareness. TNNs revolutionized sequence-to-sequence tasks, replacing recurrent layers with an architecture entirely based on the attention mechanism. Recent studies have shown that TNNs are effective in antenna and radar systems with a strong potential to capture complex dependencies in high-dimensional signal environments [41]. Particularly, in beamforming applications, TNNs have been employed for proactive 3D beamforming by analyzing historical data to predict future signal DoA [42]. Moreover, in specialized domains such as rate-splitting multiple access (RSMA) networks, TNNs have shown considerable promise in predicting channel state information, leading to more efficient predictive beamforming strategies [43]. TNNs have also demonstrated robustness in generating beamforming weights under imperfect CSI conditions [44], and have been integrated with environmental sensing data to enhance beamforming accuracy in dynamic environments [45]. In vehicular networks, TNNs have also been utilized to predict future beam directions by leveraging spatiotemporal trajectory patterns, thereby enabling mobility-aware beam management [46].

Compared to other NN architectures, TNNs facilitate the modeling of complex dependencies independent of input sequence length due to their ability to process all input elements in parallel, enhancing computational efficiency and performance, particularly on large-scale datasets. In speech processing tasks, TNNs have exhibited strong performance in capturing long-range dependencies compared to RNNs [47], [48], with the latter study emphasizing their wide-ranging efficacy across multiple domains. Moreover, TNNs offer exceptional advantages over traditional feed-forward NNs (FFNNs), achieving lower sample complexity as demonstrated in [49], while [50] shows that integrating FFNNs into TNN blocks leads to enhanced model efficiency and improved training performance.

It is worth mentioning that, in addition to the standard self-attention design, several variants of TNNs have been proposed to reduce computational complexity while enhancing efficiency. To name a few, Linformer, Performer, and Reformer reduce the complexity of the attention mechanism, making them well-suited for applications with limited resources [51]. Similarly, vision-based TNN models have introduced innovative approaches to phased array antenna optimization, significantly enhancing beamforming precision [52]. In parallel, hybrid architectures that integrate CNNs with TNNs have been highly effective in wireless communication tasks such as CSI feedback, leveraging the combined strengths of local feature extraction and global context modeling [53].

Recent developments in TNNs have notably advanced spatial signal-processing tasks, including DoA estimation and beamforming. Nevertheless, these advancements often come at the expense of increased computational complexity and inference latency. For instance, the proposed Star-Transformer [54] addresses DoA estimation by applying attention mechanisms to processed covariance matrix features. Although it demonstrates robustness in low signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) conditions, its reliance on a separate post-processing step to obtain beamforming weights limits its suitability for fully end-to-end beamforming pipelines. Similarly, [55] employs a two-stage attention mechanism, where time-domain cross-attention is used to capture spatial features from noisy covariance matrices, followed by frequency-domain self-attention to refine inter-band representations. While this structure enhances signal separation, it introduces additional inference stages and computational overhead due to the expanded attention maps. In contrast, the proposed TBF-CM adopts a streamlined, single-pass TNN design that directly predicts complex beamforming weights from the input correlation matrix, eliminating the need for intermediate steps such as DoA estimation or steering vector reconstruction. The model is tailored for interference-heavy scenarios and remains robust even with six interference sources at 0 dB SNR, achieving a consistent mean absolute error (MAE) of approximately 0.2407. With an average inference time below 0.30 milliseconds per sample, TBF-CM offers a compelling balance between accuracy and efficiency. Its low-latency operation and end-to-end formulation position it as a practical solution for real-time adaptive beamforming, outperforming more complex TNN-based alternatives in both speed and deployment readiness. Importantly, while the reviewed studies vary in their specific objectives and input formulations, they collectively underscore the growing potential of TNN-based architectures in electromagnetic and antenna-related applications. Building on this foundation, our work extends this emerging paradigm by demonstrating the effectiveness of TNNs for direct beamforming weight prediction under highly congested and low-SNR scenarios.

III. TBF-CM : PROBLEM FORMULATION

In this section, we will develop a 1-D beamformer that leverages the correlation matrix information of several signals received by a ULA to precisely predict the complex feeding weights of the ULA elements. The ULA under consideration

has M elements that are uniformly spaced at a distance of $d = \lambda/2$, where λ represents the wavelength. As illustrated in Fig. 1, the ULA receives $N + 1$ monochromatic signals. The first incoming signal is commonly known as the desired incoming signal (DIS), denoted as $s_0(k)$, and characterized by an AoA value of θ_0 . The remaining signals, denoted as $(s_n(k), n = 1, \dots, N)$, are commonly known as undesirable incoming signals (UISs) or interference signals, and they are associated with corresponding AoAs $\theta_n, n = 1, \dots, N$. The vector of the input signals is expressed as:

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = \mathbf{a}_0 s_0(k) + \mathbf{A} \mathbf{s}(k) + \mathbf{n}(k) \quad (1)$$

where

$$\mathbf{x}(k) = [x_1(k) \dots x_M(k)]^T, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathbf{s}(k) = [s_0(k) \ s_1(k) \ \dots \ s_N(k)]^T, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathbf{A} = [\mathbf{a}_0 \ \mathbf{a}_1 \ \dots \ \mathbf{a}_N], \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{a}_n = [1 \ e^{j\beta d \cos \theta_n} \ \dots \ e^{j(M-1)\beta d \cos \theta_n}]^T, \quad (5)$$

$$\mathbf{n}(k) = [n_1(k) \ \dots \ n_M(k)]^T \quad (6)$$

In this model, $\mathbf{x}(k)$ is the vector of signals at the inputs of the array elements at time instant k , \mathbf{a}_0 denotes the steering vector of the DIS, $\mathbf{a}(n)$, for $n=1, \dots, N$, are the steering vectors of the UISs, $\mathbf{s}(k)$ and \mathbf{A} represent, respectively, the vector of all incoming signals and their steering matrix, β is the free-space wavenumber, $\mathbf{n}(k)$ is the noise vector, and T denotes the transpose operation.

Fig. 1: Beamformer using a uniform linear array composed of M elements.

The formulation for the output of the array, $y(k)$, can be expressed as follows:

$$y(k) = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{x}(k), \quad (7)$$

where \mathbf{w} is the array weight vector, expressed as

$$\mathbf{w} = [w_1 \ w_2 \ \dots \ w_M]^T, \quad (8)$$

and H denotes the Hermitian (conjugate transpose) operation.

The correlation matrices represent the correlation coefficients among all potential pairings of antennas within an array. The purpose of these matrices is to analyze the received signals and detect any patterns or correlations that may be present among them. The array correlation matrix, represented as \mathbf{R}_{xx} , with a dimension of $(M \times M)$, can be defined as:

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx} = \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{x}\mathbf{x}^H] \quad (9)$$

Assuming the absence of correlation between any incoming signal ($s_n(k), n = 0, 1, \dots, N$), and any noise signal, (9) can be analyzed as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R}_{xx} &= \mathbb{E}[(\mathbf{A}\mathbf{s} + \mathbf{n})(\mathbf{s}^H \mathbf{A}^H + \mathbf{n}^H)] \\ &= \mathbf{A}\mathbb{E}[\mathbf{s}\mathbf{s}^H] \mathbf{A}^H + \mathbb{E}[\mathbf{n}\mathbf{n}^H] \\ &= \mathbf{A}\mathbf{R}_{ss} \mathbf{A}^H + \mathbf{R}_{nn}, \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where \mathbf{R}_{ss} and \mathbf{R}_{nn} represent, respectively, the signal and noise correlation matrices. Assuming the absence of correlation between any two incoming signals ($s_n(k), n = 0, 1, \dots, N$), as well as the absence of correlation between any two noise signals, \mathbf{R}_{ss} and \mathbf{R}_{nn} can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}_{ss} = P_S \mathbf{I}_{(N+1) \times (N+1)}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathbf{R}_{nn} = P_n \mathbf{I}_{M \times M}, \quad (12)$$

where P_n and P_S represent the mean power values of noise signals and incoming signals, respectively, while \mathbf{I} is the identity matrix. Based on (11), and (12), \mathbf{R}_{xx} can be expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{R}_{xx} = \mathbf{A} P_S \mathbf{I}_{(N+1) \times (N+1)} \mathbf{A}^H + P_n \mathbf{I}_{M \times M} \quad (13)$$

The initial SNR is set at 0dB, $P_S = 1$ W, and P_n can be derived by:

$$P_n = 10^{-\text{SNR}/10} \quad (14)$$

Given the superiority of NSB algorithms over traditional techniques in accurately positioning nulls toward the directions of interference signals, we can calculate the weights based on this algorithm as follows:

$$\mathbf{w}_{\text{NSB}} = \mathbf{A}(\mathbf{A}^H \mathbf{A})^{-1} \mathbf{u}_1, \quad (15)$$

where,

$$\mathbf{u}_1 = [1 \ 0 \ \dots \ 0]^T, \quad (16)$$

is the unit vector consisting of $N + 1$ elements. The following subsections present the dataset generation methodology and the evaluation metrics used in this study.

A. Dataset Generation

To train the NN-based beamformers within a supervised learning framework, the first step is creating datasets that capture the complex relationship between received signal statistics and the target optimal beamforming weights. Each input sample is a spatial correlation matrix \mathbf{R}_{xx} with dimensions ($M \times M$) (with $M = 16$ antenna elements), as defined in (13), and the corresponding output is the complex-valued weight vector \mathbf{w} , derived from (15). The overall design of the NN-based beamformer is depicted in Fig. 2. To assess generalization across diverse interference conditions, we simulate five distinct signal scenarios with $N = 3$ to 7 incoming signals. The first signal is designated as DIS, while the remaining N signals act as UISs. For each scenario, a separate dataset is generated, with incoming signal angles uniformly sampled within the range $[30^\circ, 150^\circ]$, and a minimum angular separation of $\Delta\theta \geq 6^\circ$ enforced to ensure spatial resolvability. Given that NNs typically process real-valued inputs, both \mathbf{R}_{xx} and \mathbf{w} are decomposed into their real and imaginary

parts, doubling their dimensionality. Furthermore, since \mathbf{R}_{xx} is Hermitian, we retain only its upper triangular part (excluding the diagonal) to eliminate redundancy. This reduces the input dimensionality from $2 \times M \times M$ to $2 \times \frac{M(M-1)}{2}$, improving computational efficiency and accelerating the training process.

The datasets utilized in this study are generated using MATLAB[®]. Each dataset is structured to include 900,000 records for training the NNs, 100,000 records for validation, and another 100,000 record for testing. This distribution ensures robust training while enabling effective evaluation of the performance of the NNs on unseen data.

Fig. 2: The basic framework of the NN-based beamformer.

B. Assessment Metrics

This study employs key performance metrics to evaluate the investigated NNs, including MAE, which quantifies the absolute differences between predicted and true beamforming weights. It is used during training, validation, and testing:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{P} \sum_{i=1}^P |w_{\text{pred},i} - w_{\text{true},i}|, \quad (17)$$

with P representing the total number of predicted weights, $w_{\text{pred},i}$ is the i th predicted weight, and $w_{\text{true},i}$ is the corresponding true weight.

Root mean squared error (RMSE) and Huber loss are used on the independent test set to evaluate model performance. RMSE emphasizes larger errors, while Huber loss combines the advantages of MAE and RMSE by applying a quadratic penalty to small errors and a linear penalty to large ones. They are defined as follows:

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{P} \sum_{i=1}^P (w_{\text{pred},i} - w_{\text{true},i})^2} \quad (18)$$

$$L_\delta(w_{\text{pred}}, w_{\text{true}}) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{2}(w_{\text{pred}} - w_{\text{true}})^2, & \text{if } |w_{\text{pred}} - w_{\text{true}}| \leq \delta \\ \delta(|w_{\text{pred}} - w_{\text{true}}| - \frac{1}{2}\delta), & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (19)$$

where δ represents a tunable threshold that controls the transition between quadratic and linear loss behavior.

Additionally, to evaluate the spatial performance of the predicted beamforming weights, the average radiation pattern is computed using the array factor (AF), expressed as:

$$\text{AF}(\theta) = \sum_{n=0}^{M-1} w_n^* e^{jn\pi \cos(\theta)} \quad (20)$$

TABLE I: Summary of NN architectures and training configuration

Parameter	TNN	ResNet	CNN
Input Shape	Upper triangular part of \mathbf{R}_{xx}	Upper triangular part of \mathbf{R}_{xx}	Upper triangular part of \mathbf{R}_{xx}
Preprocessing	Min-max normalization	Min-max normalization	Min-max normalization
Core Architecture	3 Transformer blocks	Conv1D + 3 residual blocks	3 convolutional blocks
Key Components	4-head self-attention, FFNN, residuals, dropout (0.2)	Skip connections, ReLU, dropout (0.3)	MaxPooling, ReLU
Pooling	Global average pooling	Global average pooling	Global average pooling
Output Dimension	$2 \times M$	$2 \times M$	$2 \times M$
Optimizer	SGD	SGD	SGD
Learning Rate	0.001	0.001	0.001
Epochs	100	100	100
Batch Size	1024	1024	1024
Training Platform	Google Colab (GPU)	Google Colab (GPU)	Google Colab (GPU)

where w_n represents the complex beamforming weight of the n th antenna element, θ is the observation angle, while n denotes the array element index. Radiation patterns are evaluated over $\theta \in [30^\circ, 150^\circ]$ with 1000 discrete sampling points, using both predicted (w_{pred}) and true (w_{true}) weights, normalized to unit peak. The average normalized pattern across S test samples is given by:

$$P_{\text{avg}}(\theta) = \frac{1}{S} \sum_{i=1}^S \frac{|AF_i(\theta)|}{\max(|AF_i(\theta)|)}, \quad (21)$$

and is converted to decibels as:

$$P_{dB}(\theta) = 20 \log_{10}(P_{\text{avg}}(\theta)) \quad (22)$$

In addition to accuracy metrics, the prediction time of each NN is recorded to assess its feasibility for real-time beamforming applications by including both the total inference time across all test samples and the average prediction time per sample.

IV. NEURAL NETWORKS DESIGN AND TRAINING CONFIGURATION

It is widely known that making NNs achieve optimal performance is a complex task due to the various hyperparameters that significantly impact the behavior of NNs. This process demands substantial computational resources and extensive processing time. Several hyperparameter tuning techniques are frequently employed to identify the optimal configurations. However, these techniques can be both computationally intensive and challenging to implement effectively. In this study, rather than relying on automated hyperparameter optimization techniques, the NN architecture was carefully tailored through empirical assessment over a range of configurations. This approach allowed us to identify the model settings that effectively address the challenges of the beamforming task under consideration. Extensive simulation tests were conducted to evaluate the performance of different architectures under different signal conditions. In particular, we employed a TBF-CM-based model to assess its suitability for beamforming applications, comparing it comprehensively against ResNet and CNN architectures to analyze their relative strengths and limitations.

This comparison emphasizes the unique ability of TNNs to model global dependencies via the self-attention mechanism that allows the model to capture spatial relationships across antenna elements embedded in the correlation matrix, which is essential for managing multiple interference sources in dynamic environments. In contrast, ResNet employs residual blocks with skip connections that pass the input of each block directly to its output, enhancing training efficiency and mitigating vanishing gradient issues. CNNs, meanwhile, excel at processing grid-structured data and have been effectively applied to beamforming problems framed as classification tasks. Detailed descriptions of the NN architectures and training configurations are provided in Table I and Fig. 3. Additionally, a high-level overview of the data preparation and training workflow is provided by Algorithm 1.

V. SIMULATION RESULTS

This section presents the results of simulation experiments conducted to evaluate TBF-CM against ResNet and CNN over scenarios with varying numbers of incoming signals (3 to 7). Performance is assessed using key metrics, including MAE, RMSE, Huber loss, prediction time, and average radiation pattern comparisons, providing a comprehensive analysis of the efficacy and accuracy of each model.

A. Prediction Accuracy

This subsection presents the simulation results based on the MAE trend observed during training over 100 epochs. Additionally, the prediction accuracy of the models is evaluated on unseen test data to measure their generalization performance, along with an analysis of their prediction times.

After training and validating the three NN models for 100 epochs across multiple signal scenarios, the MAE values of the validation phase are summarized in Table II. Additionally, Fig. 4 illustrates the MAE trends during validation across different signal scenarios, while Fig. 5 presents a direct comparison of the final MAE values for both the training and validation phases, offering a clear evaluation of the generalization capability of each model.

The TBF-CM model converges more rapidly than ResNet and CNN, consistently achieving lower validation MAE values

Fig. 3: The basic model architectures employed in the featured methodology. (a) TNN, (b) ResNet, and (c) CNN.

Fig. 4: Validation MAE over epochs for TBF-CM, ResNet, and CNN models across different signal scenarios.

across all incoming signal scenarios (see Fig. 4). This performance underscores its efficacy in capturing complex data relationships. Additionally, the stable validation curve highlights the efficiency of the model in learning optimal mappings, ensuring dependable operation under various conditions.

As evidenced by the final MAE results in Fig. 5, TBF-CM also scales effectively to challenging scenarios with six or seven incoming signals. Furthermore, the narrow and manageable gap between training and validation MAE affirms the balanced generalization capability of the model.

After completing the training and validation phases, the models were evaluated on an independent test set consisting of previously unseen correlation matrices to assess their ability to accurately predict beamforming weights. The evaluation criteria included prediction accuracy, measured using MAE, RMSE, and Huber loss, as well as computational efficiency,

TABLE II: Final validation MAE values

Signals	Model	Validation MAE
3	TBF-CM	0.2240
	ResNet	0.2727
	CNN	0.2498
4	TBF-CM	0.2366
	ResNet	0.2687
5	CNN	0.2553
	TBF-CM	0.2407
	ResNet	0.2624
6	CNN	0.2552
	TBF-CM	0.2409
	ResNet	0.2577
7	CNN	0.2522
	TBF-CM	0.2407
	ResNet	0.2530
	CNN	0.2497

Algorithm 1 Dataset generation, training, and evaluation Pipeline

Require: ULA with $M=16$ elements; signal scenarios $N \in \{3, \dots, 7\}$; AoA range $[30^\circ, 150^\circ]$ with minimum angular separation $\Delta\theta \geq 6^\circ$

Ensure: Trained models and evaluation metrics

- 1: **Dataset Generation**
 - 2: **for** each scenario **do**
 - 3: Generate $N + 1$ AoAs satisfying angular constraints
 - 4: Compute optimal complex weights $\mathbf{w} \in \mathbb{C}^M$ using NSB algorithm and store them
 - 5: Simulate received signals and compute correlation matrix $\mathbf{R}_{xx} \in \mathbb{C}^{M \times M}$
 - 6: Extract real and imaginary parts of upper triangular entries of \mathbf{R}_{xx} as input features
 - 7: Save feature-label pair $(\mathbf{R}_{xx}^{\text{up}}, \mathbf{w})$ to dataset
 - 8: **end for**
 - 9: Normalize input features using min-max scaling and split dataset into training, validation, and test sets
 - 10: **Model Training**
 - 11: **for** each architecture $\{\text{TNN}, \text{ResNet}, \text{CNN}\}$ **do**
 - 12: Initialize model with parameters (see Table I)
 - 13: Train for 100 epochs using SGD (learning rate = 0.001, batch size = 1024), monitoring MAE
 - 14: Use model trained for 100 epochs for evaluation
 - 15: **end for**
 - 16: **Model Evaluation**
 - 17: **for** each test sample **do**
 - 18: Predict weights $\hat{\mathbf{w}}$ and measure inference time
 - 19: Compute MAE, RMSE, and Huber loss
 - 20: Derive radiation pattern from predicted weights using the array factor equation
 - 21: **end for**
 - 22: Report average error metrics, radiation patterns, and mean inference time
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Fig. 5: Final MAE values for varying numbers of incoming signals during training and validation (note: CNN training and validation results overlap).

assessed in terms of inference time.

Figs. 6, 7, and 8 illustrate error trends for TBF-CM, ResNet, and CNN across different numbers of incoming sig-

Fig. 6: Comparison of RMSE across NN models on an independent test set.

Fig. 7: Comparison of MAE across NN models on an independent test set.

Fig. 8: Comparison of Huber loss across NN models on an independent test set.

nals. TBF-CM consistently achieves the lowest RMSE, MAE, and Huber loss, particularly when the number of signals is high, reflecting its strong generalization and adaptability in complex beamforming scenarios. Although CNN delivers a competitive performance, it marginally lags behind TBF-CM in accuracy. In contrast, ResNet exhibits higher RMSE, MAE, and Huber loss overall but shows steady improvement as the signal count increases. Consequently, TBF-CM emerges as the most effective model, providing more accurate and stable beamforming weight predictions, making it both scalable and reliable for adaptive beamforming applications.

In Table III and Fig. 9, the computational efficiency of each model is compared by examining inference time per sample. Although ResNet delivers the quickest inference speed, its relatively higher prediction errors underscore a trade-off between

Fig. 9: Comparison of average prediction time per sample across NN models on an independent test set.

accuracy and computational efficiency. By contrast, TBF-CM maintains both high predictive accuracy and moderate inference times, making it particularly well-suited for real-time beamforming tasks. Meanwhile, CNN, despite offering competitive accuracy, exhibits the highest computational cost, which may restrict its suitability in latency-critical settings.

TABLE III: Inference time for various NN models

Signals	Model	Total Prediction Time (ms)	Avg. Time per Sample (ms)
3	TBF-CM	29813.3	0.29813
	ResNet	12073.6	0.12074
	CNN	41333.9	0.41334
4	TBF-CM	29574.6	0.29575
	ResNet	11990.9	0.11991
	CNN	40816.6	0.40817
5	TBF-CM	29299.0	0.29299
	ResNet	11662.8	0.11663
	CNN	41901.4	0.41901
6	TBF-CM	29505.1	0.29505
	ResNet	12054.0	0.12054
	CNN	42146.0	0.42146
7	TBF-CM	29345.8	0.29346
	ResNet	12284.2	0.12284
	CNN	42791.7	0.42792

These findings highlight the balance between prediction accuracy and inference speed and offer crucial insights for implementing DL-based beamforming methods in practice. In this scenario, TBF-CM stands out by striking an optimal compromise between precision and computational efficiency. However, in practical deployment scenarios, balancing inference time with model complexity is essential. Therefore, future work would consider further optimizing the TBF-CM architecture. This can be done by adjusting the depth of the TNN blocks and the number of attention heads or by exploring lightweight variants of TNN-based models, which also preserve the potential of capturing global spatial dependencies [56]–[58]. Lastly, several compression techniques, such as pruning and knowledge distillation [33], [59], could help further reduce the inference time without compromising the prediction accuracy.

B. Performance Evaluation in Terms of Radiation Patterns

Beyond numerical metrics, it is crucial to assess model performance using a domain-specific evaluation, such as radiation pattern accuracy, which reflects the ability of the beamformer

Fig. 10: Radiation pattern comparison between the predicted TBF-CM pattern and the true pattern.

Fig. 11: Radiation pattern comparison between the predicted ResNet pattern and the true pattern.

to replicate the actual array response across different angles. Figs 10, 11, and 12 illustrate the predicted beam patterns generated by TBF-CM, ResNet, and CNN, respectively, compared against the ground truth that represents a reference benchmark and is generated using the ground-truth complex-valued weights from the test set. In the presented figures, the angles annotated along the horizontal axis represent the analytically computed null positions in the radiation pattern of a 16-element ULA, with the main lobe steered toward 70° . These positions indicate directions of expected destructive interference and serve as reference points for evaluating how accurately each model replicates the spatial characteristics of the true radiation pattern.

TBF-CM demonstrates a high degree of fidelity to the true radiation pattern, accurately steering the main lobe and maintaining stable side lobe levels. It exhibits only minor discrepancies in null positions, indicating strong generalization across diverse beamforming scenarios. ResNet, meanwhile, excels in null formation by effectively capturing deep nulls, though it shows slight variations in side lobes, suggesting

Fig. 12: Radiation pattern comparison between the predicted CNN pattern and the true pattern.

challenges in precise amplitude control. Although the CNN aligns the main lobe accurately, its larger deviations in side lobe levels and null depths highlight limitations in modeling the finer details of beamforming weight distributions. Overall, TBF-CM emerges as the most precise method, achieving an optimal balance between beamforming accuracy and computational efficiency. ResNet follows closely, demonstrating robust null-forming capabilities. CNN, while competitive, displays more pronounced variability in side lobes, which may limit its effectiveness in high-interference environments. These findings underscore the advanced learning potential of deep learning-based beamforming methods, with TBF-CM offering the most favorable trade-off between radiation pattern fidelity and real-time feasibility.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This study introduced TBF-CM, a transformer designed to predict beamforming weights using correlation matrix data. Extensive evaluations across various multi-signal scenarios revealed that TBF-CM consistently outperforms CNN and ResNet, achieving lower RMSE, MAE, and Huber loss. Its strong generalization is particularly evident in complex environments. While ResNet offers faster inference, TBF-CM maintains an optimal balance between accuracy and efficiency, making it well-suited for real-time beamforming tasks. Additionally, radiation pattern analyses confirmed the precision of the model in steering the main lobe, positioning nulls accurately, and suppressing side lobes.

Overall, TBF-CM emerges as a compelling alternative to standard NN-based beamformers, leveraging self-attention mechanisms to deliver robust performance under dynamic conditions. Nevertheless, when scaling to larger antenna arrays with more complex geometries, the model may encounter limitations. These arise primarily from the increased input dimensionality, which can introduce significant computational overhead, ultimately impacting both inference time and memory requirements. Moreover, dynamic environments characterized by user mobility and varying interference patterns demand

highly adaptive mechanisms to maintain reliable performance. Future research will aim to enhance inference speed without compromising accuracy while also exploring meta-learning, model compression, and architectural adaptations to improve scalability and robustness in real-time, non-stationary environments.

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